

PRESCHOOL - EDUCATIONAL ORGANIZATION - A PLACE OF SOCIAL EDUCATION OF CHILDREN OF PRESCHOOL AGE.

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Abstract: The success of the learning process largely depends on the provisions that guide the teacher in his organization. These provisions or laws of education are called in pedagogy - didactic principles. The principles of teaching are the starting points that determine the nature of the activities of the teacher and children.

Key concepts: national training program, state, society, lifelong education, law, personality, educational process, production, humanization, democratization of education.

Аннотация: Успешность процесса обучения во многом зависит от положений, которыми руководствуется педагог в его организации. Данные положения или законы обучения получили в педагогике название - дидактические принципы. Принципы обучения - это исходные положения, определяющие характер деятельности педагога и детей.

Ключевые понятия: национальная программа по подготовке кадров, государство, общество, непрерывное образование, закон, личность, учебный процесс, производство, гуманизация, демократизация образования.

The Republic of Uzbekistan is building a democratic rule of law and an open civil society that ensures the observance of human rights and freedoms, the spiritual renewal of society, the formation of a socially oriented market economy, and integration into the world community.

The main goal and driving force of the transformations being implemented in the republic is a person, his harmonious development and well-being, the creation of conditions and effective mechanisms for realizing the interests of the individual, changing obsolete stereotypes of thinking and social behavior.

An important condition for the development of Uzbekistan is the formation of a perfect system of training based on the rich intellectual heritage of the people and human values, the achievements of modern culture, economics, science, technology and technology.

The national training program complies with the provisions of the Law of the Republic of Uzbekistan "On Education", developed on the basis of an analysis of national experience, based on world achievements in the education system and is focused on the formation of a new generation of personnel with a high general and professional culture, creative and social activity, the ability to independently navigate social and political life, capable of setting and solving tasks for the future.

The program provides for the implementation of the national model of personnel training, the creation of socio-economic, legal, psychological, pedagogical and other conditions for the formation of a comprehensively developed personality, adaptation to life in a modern changing society, conscious choice and subsequent development of educational and professional programs, education of citizens who are aware of their responsibility to society, the state and the family.

As stipulated by the National Program for Personnel Training, the implementation of reforms in the field of education is carried out in three stages in parallel with phased reforms in other areas of the life of the republic.

The principles of teaching are the starting points that determine the nature of the activities of the teacher and children. The success of the learning process largely depends on the provisions that guide the teacher in his organization. These provisions or laws of education are called in pedagogy - didactic principles. Didactic

principles were first formulated by Jan Amos Comenius in the 17th century in the book *Great Didactics, or How to Teach Everything to Everyone*.

Subsequently, K.D. Ushinsky gave them a scientific justification, based on the achievements of physiology and psychology of the 19th century. Modern didactics highlights a number of teaching principles. The principle of developmental education. Training should lead development - this position of L.S. Vygotsky underlies the organization of interaction between the teacher and the child. The bottom line is that learning should not focus only on the achieved level, but always get ahead of it, so that the child expends effort to master new material.

Both the content of the training and its methods should be accessible. This principle underlies the content of all educational programs; children should, first of all, study those objects and phenomena of the world around them that are understandable and accessible to them. Ya.A. Comenius formulated this principle as follows: "From close to distant, from simple to complex, from familiar to unfamiliar." The principle of consistency and consistency. New knowledge should always be based on the child's knowledge, be associated with it and contribute to the strengthening and refinement of it.

Based on the consistent accumulation of knowledge about the world around children, a system of knowledge, generalized concepts is formed. The principle of consciousness and activity of children in the assimilation and application of knowledge. Research scientists have proven that knowledge is strong when it is conscious and comprehended. The mastering of knowledge is the more effective, the more actively the child operates with them. To develop the activity of children in the learning process, the teacher uses various techniques: questions, comparisons, problem situations, elementary experiments, heuristic conversations, etc. The principle of visibility. Since the thinking of a preschooler is visual and visual-figurative, this principle is of particular importance in teaching children.

The use of various types of visualization - the observation of living objects, the examination of objects, pictures, samples, the use of TSO, the use of diagrams, models in the learning process, etc. - contributes to the conscious perception of those phenomena and objects that an adult introduces children to. Ya.A. Comenius considered it the "golden rule" of didactics. The principle of an individual approach to children. The individual characteristics of the development of children dictate the need to take them into account in the process of teaching children.

A differentiated approach to teaching requires a certain flexibility from the educator, all tasks that children receive must correspond to their level of proximal development, therefore the degree of complexity of tasks should be different for each child, since children can develop in different ways. Two models have developed in preschool education: traditional (authoritarian, educational and disciplinary model) and personality-oriented. Traditional: the goal is to equip children with knowledge, skills and abilities, instill obedience, reproductive activity. The results of preschool education were evaluated by the amount of knowledge: it was believed that the more "invested" in the child, the more successfully he was taught. A distinctive feature of the educational and disciplinary model was the uniformity of the content, methods and forms of education, i.e. training was carried out according to uniform programs, curricula and manuals.

Ways of communication - instructions, explanations, prohibition, demands, threats, punishments. The task of the teacher is to implement the program, meet the requirements of the management and controlling authorities. The child is the object of application of the forces of the educational system. The center of the pedagogical process is the frontal forms of work with children, the classroom system, the activity of children is suppressed, the game is strictly regulated and infringed. Results: mutual alienation of adults and children, loss of initiative by children, negativism. The acute need of modern society for people with independent, creative thinking prompted scientists (Sh.A. Amonashvili, V.V. Davydov, V.A. Petrovsky and others)

to develop a different model of education based on a personality-oriented interaction between the educator and the child.

The purpose of such training is the development of intellectual; spiritual, physical abilities, interests and motives of activity, including educational (i.e., the personal development of the child), the acquisition of himself as a unique individuality. To achieve this goal, the child, starting from the early years of life, should support the desire to join the world of human culture by mastering the means and methods transferred to him, which are necessary for this inclusion. The educator needs to organize the children and involve them in an active process of solving cognitive and practical problems, during which each child could feel his growth, the joy of creativity and improvement. The personality-oriented model of interaction between the educator and the child has its own pedagogical technology: the transition from explanation to understanding, from monologue to dialogue, from social control to development, from management to self-government. At the same time, learning is realized in joint activities, cooperation between the educator and children, in which the educator is an assistant, adviser, elder friend on the basis of the following positions of its participants: subject-object model - an adult is in relation to children in the position of a teacher, setting certain tasks for them and offering specific ways and actions to resolve them; object-subject model - an adult creates a developing environment, a kind of objective world in which children act freely and independently; subject-subject model - the position of equal partners included in a common joint activity.

All the presented models take place in the real pedagogical process of the preschool educational institution, and their use depends on the need to solve various educational problems. In this regard, modern works consider various forms of organization of the learning process associated with these positional models.

Types of children's education are revealed in the works of T.A. Kulikova: a) Direct teaching - the educator defines a didactic task, puts it in front of the children,

gives a sample of performance, in the course of completing the task, directs the activities of each child to achieve a result. The transfer of information from children to adults, when children act independently, and an adult observes their activities. b) Problem-based learning: preschoolers are not offered ready-made knowledge, but they create a problem situation that cannot be solved with the help of existing knowledge and skills. To do this, he must turn over his experience, establish in it other connections, dependencies between phenomena. The problem situation is solved in the process of collective search activity, which is accompanied by a heuristic conversation. The teacher's questions relate to comparison, comparison of facts, etc. Equal search for solutions by adults and children as subjects of activity problems during observation, discussion and experimentation. c) Indirect learning is carried out in two ways: 1) children are offered a task with an incomplete enumeration of the conditions and sequence of its solution, while each child performs his own version of solving the task; 2) children are offered various materials, and they determine the task of the activity, its content; d) Indirect learning lies in the fact that the teacher, on the basis of the collected data on the development of children, organizes the object-spatial environment: consistently selects certain means with which you can optimize the learning process (sets of games, equipment for experiments, books, toys, etc.).

Then it is necessary to include these funds in the activities of children, enrich its content, influence the development of communication, business cooperation (for example, children exchange impressions about where they were in the summer, and the teacher takes out an atlas and visually find, examine and study together). The organization on the basis of the presented models of educational and educational work with children is carried out by creating problem-playing, developing, educational situations.

When organizing the educational process, it is also necessary to take into account the following principles: - the principle of developmental education (one of the tasks

of education is the development of a preschooler); - the principle of the unity of educational, developing and teaching goals and objectives of the education of preschool children; - combination of principles of scientific validity and practical applicability of knowledge; - the principle of integration of educational areas in accordance with the age capabilities and characteristics of pupils; - complex-thematic principle of building the educational process.

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